

Letter accompanies ~~adpart~~
application for extension of BIPS Fellowship
1970-71.

British Institute of Persian Studies
P.O. box 2617,
Teheran,
Iran.
26/5/1970.

Dear Mr. Gueritz,

I enclose a copy of an application to renew
my current Fellowship of the British Institute of Persian
Studies for the year 1970-1971. This consists of:

Curriculum vitae.
Progress of research.
Explanation of research.
Projected research.
Prior financial support.
Details of funds requested.

You will notice that although this is primarily
an application to the major Fellowship Fund I intend to spend
some time at Siraf so that this part of the Fund is also concerned.

Seven duplicate copies of this application are
being sent under separate cover.

I must again apologize for leaving this application
to the very last minute.

Yours sincerely,

Andrew Williamson.